

VIBRATION ANALYSIS OF THICK LAMINATED TRAPEZOIDAL PLATES

C.C. Chen¹, C.W. Lim¹, S. Kitipornchai¹, and K.M. Liew²

¹ *Department of Civil Engineering, The University of Queensland, Qld 4072, Australia*

² *Division of Engineering Mechanics, School of Mechanical and Production Engineering, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore 639798*

SUMMARY: To account for the effect of transverse shear deformation, the p -Ritz method incorporating Reddy's third-order shear deformation theory has been developed for the free vibration analysis of thick, laminated, cantilever, trapezoidal plates. In the proposed p -Ritz method, sets of uniquely defined polynomial functions are used as the admissible trial displacement and rotation functions. The admissible function consists of the product of a two-dimensional function and a basic function which is defined by multiplying the equations of the plate's prescribed boundary. The total energy is derived by using Reddy's third-order shear deformation theory which is able to predict the vibration characteristics of thick laminates more accurately. A convergence study has been carried out to verify the accuracy of the results. The results, wherever possible, are compared with published solutions to demonstrate the versatility and applicability of the proposed method.

KEYWORDS: free vibration, laminate, plate, higher-order shear deformation theory, p -Ritz method

INTRODUCTION

The characteristics of high tensile strength and light weight has made the laminated plates gained their popularity in aerospace and marine engineering applications. Therefore, the ability to accurately determine the structural behavior of these panels is of paramount importance. The use of shear deformation theories for the analysis of thick laminated composite plates has emerged because of the inadequacy of the classical laminated plate theory [1] based on the Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis. The most popular shear deformation theory is the first-order shear deformation theory [2] which was extended to laminates by Yang *et al.*[3] In this theory, a shear correction factor is assumed a priori and it doesn't account for surfaces free of transverse shear strains. In an effort to circumvent the drawbacks of the first order shear deformation, various second and higher-order shear deformation theories have been proposed. The most common higher-order theory was pioneered by Levinson [4] and Reddy [5,6] which assumes transverse inextensibility. The present method adopts the simple higher-order theory based on the pioneering work of Reddy [5].

The need of wing-type structures has facilitated the development of trapezoidal laminates. Not much research in this topic have been done so far. Lee and Lee [7] applied the finite element method incorporating the first-order theory to investigate the vibration problem of moderately thick, cantilevered, trapezoidal laminates. Kapania and Lovejoy [8] used Chebychev

polynomials as displacement functions in the Rayleigh-Ritz method and utilized the first-order theory to study the free vibration of moderately thick, generally laminated, cantilevered, quadrilateral plates. Liew and Lim [9] integrated the classical theory and p -Ritz method for the problem of thin trapezoidal laminates. The p -Ritz method which developed by Liew [10] avoids the difficulty of mesh generation and continuity conditions required in discretization methods and is applicable to laminates with free, simply supported and clamped edge conditions. In this study, the p -Ritz method incorporating Reddy's third-order shear deformation theory is proposed for the vibration analysis of cantilevered, thick, laminated, trapezoidal plates. Convergence of frequency parameters has been carried out to ensure adequate terms in the displacement and rotation functions. The effects of aspect ratio, taper ratio, plate geometry and stacking angle on the thick, cantilevered, trapezoidal laminate are also investigated. The results, wherever possible, are compared with published solutions to evaluate the validity and to demonstrate the applicability of the proposed method.

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATIONS

Preliminary Definitions

Fig. 1 illustrates a thick, cantilever, laminated, trapezoidal plate composed of N orthotropic laminae oriented at angle θ_k with respect to the x -axis and with the geometric configuration of

length-to-thickness ratio a/h , aspect ratio a/b , taper ratio c/b , skew angle γ , and total thickness h . The reference Cartesian coordinate system is located at the mid-plane of the laminated plate. The angle γ which measures positive in the clockwise direction, is the degree of skewness of the trapezoidal laminate. Another two definitions of the skew angles, α and β , are also used for the convenience of comparison. The laminae are cross-plyed or stacked symmetrically with respect to the middle surface of the laminated plate. The interior angles of laminate geometries are assumed to be no larger than 90 degrees. The vibration frequencies of the trapezoidal laminate subjected to a variety of skewness angles, aspect ratios, taper ratios, and stacking angles are to be determined.

Fig. 1: Laminated trapezoidal plate geometry

Energy Expressions

For a thick trapezoidal laminate undergoing small-amplitude vibration, the spatial displacement at a general point may be resolved into u , v (in-plane motion) and w (out-of-plane motion) components, respectively. By using Reddy's higher-order shear deformation theory, the displacement field along the x -, y -, z -axis can be expressed in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z, t) &= u_0(x, y, t) + z\phi_x(x, y, t) - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2} \left(\phi_x(x, y, t) + \frac{\partial w(x, y, t)}{\partial x} \right) \\ v(x, y, z, t) &= v_0(x, y, t) + z\phi_y(x, y, t) - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2} \left(\phi_y(x, y, t) + \frac{\partial w(x, y, t)}{\partial y} \right) \\ w(x, y, z, t) &= w_0(x, y, t) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $(u_0, v_0, w_0, \phi_x, \phi_y)$ are the displacement components of the mid-plane along the x -, y -, and z -directions and rotations of the mid-plane about the y - and x -direction, respectively. For free vibration problem, the deflection and rotation functions of the laminate mid-plane are sinusoidal in time, that is

$$\begin{aligned} u_0(x, y, t) &= U(x, y) \sin \omega t \\ v_0(x, y, t) &= V(x, y) \sin \omega t \\ w_0(x, y, t) &= W(x, y) \sin \omega t \\ \phi_x(x, y, t) &= \Theta_u(x, y) \sin \omega t \\ \phi_y(x, y, t) &= \Theta_v(x, y) \sin \omega t \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

If the laminated plate is made of elastic materials, the strain energy for each ply is given by

$$U_k = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_k} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_k^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}_k dV_k \quad (3)$$

where U_k and V_k are the strain energy and the volume of the k th lamina, respectively. Neglecting normal stress σ_k , the total strain energy for the entire laminated plate is

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \iint_A \int_{h_{k-1}}^{h_k} (\sigma_x \varepsilon_x + \sigma_y \varepsilon_y + \sigma_{xz} \varepsilon_{xz} + \sigma_{yz} \varepsilon_{yz} + \sigma_{xy} \varepsilon_{xy})_k dz dA \quad (4)$$

Also, the total kinetic energy T associated with the vibration of laminated plate is

$$T = \frac{h}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \iint_A \rho_k \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right] dA \quad (5)$$

in which ρ_k is the mass density of the k th lamina.

The energy components U and T can be further simplified by introducing the equivalent modulus for a multidirectional lamina

$$(A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}, E_{ij}, F_{ij}, H_{ij}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{h_k}^{h_{k+1}} (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (1, z, z^2, z^3, z^4, z^6) dz \quad (6)$$

in which, $(\bar{Q}_{ij})_k$ are obtained by transforming the stacking angle θ_k and the stiffness constants, $(Q_{ij})_k$, which are related to the material properties, $E_1, E_2, \nu_{12}, \nu_{21}, G_{12}, G_{13}, G_{23}$, of each ply. Eqns (4) and (5) can be further expanded in terms of $(U, V, W, \Theta_u, \Theta_v)$ by substituting the strain-displacement relationship, stress-strain relationships and Eqn (2). As the vibration is periodic in time, we are able to obtain the maximum strain energy U_{\max} and maximum kinetic energy T_{\max} in a vibratory cycle. Finally, the total energy functional Π for the free vibration of laminated plate is defined as

$$\Pi = U_{\max} - T_{\max} \quad (7)$$

which is to be minimized by the Rayleigh-Ritz method to obtain the frequency.

***p*-Ritz Method**

The displacement and rotation components, $U(x, y)$, $V(x, y)$, $W(x, y)$, $\Theta_u(x, y)$, and $\Theta_v(x, y)$, can be further simplified by using the non-dimensional expressions

$$\xi = \frac{x}{a}, \eta = \frac{y}{b} \quad (8)$$

In the Rayleigh-Ritz method, the displacement and rotation functions should be expressed in the form of a series containing unknown coefficients,

$$\begin{aligned} U(\xi, \eta) &= \sum_{i=1}^m c_i^u \varphi_i^u(\xi, \eta) \\ V(\xi, \eta) &= \sum_{i=1}^m c_i^v \varphi_i^v(\xi, \eta) \\ W(\xi, \eta) &= \sum_{i=1}^m c_i^w \varphi_i^w(\xi, \eta) \\ \Theta_u(\xi, \eta) &= \sum_{i=1}^m c_i^{\theta_u} \varphi_i^{\theta_u}(\xi, \eta) \\ \Theta_v(\xi, \eta) &= \sum_{i=1}^m c_i^{\theta_v} \varphi_i^{\theta_v}(\xi, \eta) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $c_i^u, c_i^v, c_i^w, c_i^{\theta_u}, c_i^{\theta_v}$ are the unknown coefficients.

Now, using the *p*-Ritz method, we assumed the *p*-Ritz shape functions, $\varphi_i^u, \varphi_i^v, \varphi_i^w, \varphi_i^{\theta_u}, \varphi_i^{\theta_v}$ to be the products of two-dimensional polynomial series and basic functions. The two-dimensional polynomial series $f_i(\xi, \eta)$ are defined as

$$\sum_{i=1}^m f_i(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{q=0}^p \sum_{i=0}^q \xi^{q-i} \eta^i \quad (10)$$

where p is the highest degree of the set of two-dimensional polynomials.

To ensure automatic satisfaction of geometric boundary conditions, the basic functions are assumed to be consist of products of boundary expressions of the laminated plate raised to their associated basic powers. Thus, for the trapezoidal laminated plate shown in Fig. 1, the basic functions can be structured as shown below

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_b^\kappa = & \left(\xi + \frac{1}{2} \right)^{\Omega_1^\kappa} \left\{ \eta + \left[\frac{a}{b} \tan \beta - \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{c}{b} \right) \right] \xi + \frac{1}{4} \left(1 + \frac{c}{b} \right) \right\}^{\Omega_2^\kappa} \left(\xi - \frac{1}{2} \right)^{\Omega_3^\kappa} \\ & \times \left\{ \eta + \left[\frac{a}{b} \tan \beta + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{c}{b} \right) \right] \xi - \frac{1}{4} \left(1 + \frac{c}{b} \right) \right\}^{\Omega_4^\kappa} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where Ω_s^κ denotes the associated basic power. If the cantilevered plate clamped at $\xi = -1/2$, the basic powers Ω_s^κ are defined as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_s^\kappa &= 0, \text{ for } \kappa = u, v, w, \theta_u, \theta_v \text{ and } s = 2, 3, 4 \\ \Omega_1^\kappa &= 1, \text{ for } \kappa = u, v, w, \theta_u, \theta_v \\ \Omega_1^w &= 2, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The total energy functional Π derived in equation (7) are minimized with respect to the unknown coefficients leading to the following governing equation,

$$\frac{1}{D_0} \begin{bmatrix} K^{uu} & K^{uv} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & K^{vv} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & K^{ww} & K^{w\theta_u} & K^{w\theta_v} \\ & & & K^{\theta_u\theta_u} & K^{\theta_u\theta_v} \\ & sym. & & & K^{\theta_v\theta_v} \end{bmatrix} - \lambda \begin{bmatrix} M^{uu} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & M^{vv} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & M^{ww} & M^{w\theta_u} & M^{w\theta_v} \\ & & & M^{\theta_u\theta_u} & 0 \\ & sym. & & & M^{\theta_v\theta_v} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} c^u \\ c^v \\ c^w \\ ac^{\theta_u} \\ bc^{\theta_v} \end{Bmatrix} = 0 \quad (13)$$

with

$$D_0 = \frac{Q_{11} h^3}{12(1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21})} \quad (14)$$

Details of the stiffness and mass matrices can be found in [11]. If the laminae are made of the same material with mass density per unit volume ρ and the same thickness h , the non-dimensional eigenvalue λ becomes

$$\lambda = \omega ab \sqrt{\frac{\rho h}{D_0}} \quad (15)$$

The vibration frequencies and mode shapes of trapezoidal laminates are obtained by solving λ .

NUMERICAL STUDIES AND DISCUSSION

Numerical computation has been carried out in double precision on a *SGI PowerChallenge* computer. The results have been compared with available solutions of first-order shear deformation theory. Excellent agreement exists between the present method and previous solutions. In all examples, laminates have been assumed to be equal thickness and made of non-dimensional material properties, $E_1/E_2 = 25$, $G_{12}/E_2 = 0.5$, $G_{23}/E_2 = 0.2$, $G_{13} = G_{12}$, and $\nu = 0.25$.

Table 1: Convergence of frequency parameters λ of 6-ply trapezoidal laminates with $a/b = 1.0$, $c/b = 0.3$, stacking sequence $[30_2/0]_s$, $a/h = 5$, and $\gamma = 0$

p	Mode sequence number							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
8	2.3576	4.6118	7.1591	7.5668	9.7511	10.8658	13.4282	15.3492
10	2.3575	4.6110	7.1582	7.5668	9.7488	10.8596	13.4223	15.3365
11	2.3575	4.6108	7.1581	7.5667	9.7486	10.8584	13.4218	15.3344
12	2.3575	4.6108	7.1580	7.5667	9.7484	10.8578	13.4215	15.3337
13	2.3575	4.6107	7.1580	7.5667	9.7483	10.8573	13.4213	15.3332
14	2.3575	4.6107	7.1580	7.5667	9.7483	10.8571	13.4213	15.3330
15	2.3575	4.6107	7.1579	7.5667	9.7483	10.8569	13.4212	15.3328

The trapezoidal laminated plates with aspect ratio 1, taper ratio 0.3, length-to-thickness ratio 5, $\gamma = 0$, and stacking sequence $[30_2/0]_s$ were solved in the first example. Convergence studies have been carried out to check the numerical accuracy of this method. The degree of polynomial p was increased from 8 to 15 to study its effect on the non-dimensional frequency parameters λ . As shown in Table 1, the difference between the results for $p = 11$ and $p = 15$ are less than 0.02%. Apparently, the degree of polynomial $p = 15$ is enough to ensure the convergence of the results and it is used in all subsequent examples.

The effects of aspect ratio, taper ratio and stacking angle on the frequency parameters of moderately thick symmetric laminates have been investigated in the second example. The present method is further verified by comparing the results for frequency parameters with the solutions from Kapania and Lovejoy[8] who applied Chebychev polynomials and first-order shear deformation theory. As shown in Table 2, the results are in excellent agreement with previous solutions. It is noted that the frequency parameter decreases with increasing aspect ratio or taper ratio. The influence of aspect ratio indicates that cantilevered plates with higher a/b are structurally weaker than those with lower a/b . As for the effect of taper ratio, the authors believe that the reduction in mass for lower c/b leads to the increase of the frequency.

In the previous example, the increase in stacking angle caused different change in frequency parameter. Therefore, a cursory examination of the influence of stacking angles and taper ratios on the vibration of thick trapezoidal laminates is required. In the third example, the laminates are assumed to be stacked symmetrically with stacking sequence $[-\theta/\theta]_s$, a length-to-thickness ratio of 5, and plate geometry $\beta = 0$. By comparing the lowest four frequency results λ , the effects of taper ratio and stacking angle for laminates with different geometry have been shown in Fig.2. Again, it confirms that a lower taper ratio results in higher frequency parameter. Also note that the fundamental frequencies decrease as stacking

angle increases. For all modes except the fundamental mode, higher frequencies are likely to occur with the stacking angle between 15 and 45 degrees.

Table 2: Effects of aspect ratio, taper ratio and stacking angle on the four lowest frequency parameters, $\lambda_1 = \omega a^2 / h\sqrt{\rho / E_2}$, of laminated trapezoidal plates with $\alpha = 0$, stacking sequence $[-\theta / \theta / 0]_s$ and $a/h = 10$

a/b	c/b	θ	Mode sequence number								
			1		2		3		4		
			Ref. 8	Present	Ref. 8	Present	Ref. 8	Present	Ref. 8	Present	
1	0.25	0	6.85	6.904	11.9	12.029	14.9	14.901	22.5	23.091	
		30	5.21	5.224	16.4	16.431	19.5	19.704	32.4	32.141	
		45	3.7	3.704	14.9	14.826	17.3	17.402	32.8	32.319	
	0.50	0	6.20	6.252	9.05	9.136	13.5	13.451	18.7	18.896	
		30	4.59	4.603	12.7	12.681	18.3	18.402	27.1	26.967	
		45	3.20	3.206	13.2	13.160	14.3	14.227	29.2	28.816	
	1.00	0	5.58	5.628	6.10	6.153	9.53	9.592	11.6	11.574	
		30	4.01	4.023	8.21	8.218	14.2	14.250	19.4	19.481	
		45	2.75	2.759	8.45	8.444	13.1	13.116	20.1	20.026	
	2	0.25	0	2.05	2.052	4.93	4.945	7.14	7.131	8.67	8.761
			30	1.34	1.343	5.85	5.829	8.24	8.259	12.1	12.091
			45	0.885	0.884	4.04	4.021	8.65	8.634	10.0	10.886
0.50		0	1.80	1.803	3.53	3.536	6.41	6.399	8.32	8.408	
		30	1.16	1.155	5.58	5.557	6.19	6.209	10.9	10.895	
		45	0.755	0.754	3.86	3.849	6.50	6.489	9.87	9.852	
1.00		0	1.55	1.547	2.10	2.106	5.46	5.455	6.93	6.935	
		30	0.987	0.987	3.85	3.852	5.35	5.345	9.49	9.470	
		45	0.640	0.639	3.72	3.712	4.08	4.072	8.73	8.709	
5		0.25	0	0.361	0.361	1.46	1.461	1.75	1.753	2.24	2.176
			30	0.201	0.201	0.957	0.955	2.18	2.119	2.46	2.442
			45	0.128	0.128	0.621	0.619	1.61	1.597	1.92	1.853
	0.50	0	0.308	0.308	1.05	1.050	1.63	1.633	2.03	1.969	
		30	0.170	0.170	0.910	0.908	1.98	1.933	2.39	2.387	
		45	0.108	0.108	0.588	0.586	1.60	1.589	1.75	1.694	
	1.00	0	0.255	0.255	0.614	0.614	1.54	1.544	1.73	1.713	
		30	0.143	0.143	0.877	0.876	1.47	1.467	1.78	1.760	
		45	0.0901	0.0900	0.566	0.564	1.57	1.548	1.58	1.576	

Consideration is now given to the effect of taper ratios and plate geometry on the 8-ply anti-symmetrically cross-plyed trapezoids. Numerical results have been illustrated in Fig. 3. As anticipated, an increase in taper ratio leads to a decrease in the frequency parameter. The fundamental frequency parameter decreases as the plate geometry β increases. However, for the rest of the modes, the effect of plate geometry on the frequency parameter is significant. From the numerical results of the third and fourth examples, we may conclude that an increase in aspect ratio or taper ratio results in an decrease in frequency parameter. As for the effect of stacking angle on the frequency parameters, no theoretical explanation is available, to the authors' knowledge. However, from the results of this study, we may conclude that: 1)

for the bending modes, the frequency parameter decreases when stacking angle increases; 2) for other modes except torsional modes, the frequency parameter decreases when stacking angle approaches 0 or 75 and maximum frequency values are most likely to occur when stacking angle is between 15 and 45; 3) for the torsional modes, the change of frequency parameter is influenced by the plate geometry.

Fig. 2: Effects of taper ratio c/b and stacking angle θ on the first four non-dimensional frequency parameters λ of laminated trapezoidal plates with stacking sequence $[-\theta/\theta]_s$, $\beta = 0$ and $a/h = 5$

Fig. 3: Effects of taper ratio c/b on the first four non-dimensional frequency parameters λ of laminated trapezoidal plates with stacking sequence $[0/90]_4$ and $a/h = 5$

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an approximate method based on the Rayleigh-Ritz energy approach for the vibration analysis of thick, cantilevered, stacked symmetrically or cross-plyed trapezoidal laminates. In this method, sets of two-dimensional p -Ritz shape functions are employed as the admissible displacement and rotation functions. Since the boundary conditions have been formulated as the intrinsic components of the p -Ritz functions, the boundary conditions are automatically satisfied at the outset. Several examples have been verified and the results are in close agreement with available published literature. It can be concluded that an increase in aspect ratio or taper ratio results in a decrease in frequency parameter. In addition, both plate geometry and stacking angle should be considered as their influence on the frequency parameter are significant.

REFERENCES

1. Leissa, A.W., *Vibration of Plates*, NASA SP-160, Scientific and Technical Information Division, Office of Technology Utilization, NASA, Washington D. C., 1969.
2. Reissner, E., "The Effect of Transverse Shear Deformation on The Bending of Elastic Plates", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 12, 1945, pp. A69-A77.
3. Yang, P.C., Norris, C.H., and Stavsky, Y., "Elastic Wave Propagation in Heterogeneous Plates", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 2, 1966, pp. 665-684.
4. Levinson, M., "An Accurate Simple Theory of The Statics and Dynamics of Elastic Plates", *Mechanical Research Communications*, Vol. 7, 1980, pp. 343-350.
5. Reddy, J.N., "A Simple Higher-Order Theory for Laminated Composite Plates", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 51, 1984, pp. 745-752.
6. Reddy, J.N. and Phan, N.D., "Stability and Vibration of Isotropic, Orthotropic and Laminated Plates According to A Higher-Order Shear Deformation Theory", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 98, 1985, pp.157-170.
7. Lee, I., and Lee, J.J., "Vibration Analysis of Composite Plate Wing", *Computers and Structures*, Vol. 37, No. 6, 1990, pp. 1077-1085.
8. Kapania, R.K., and Lovejoy, E.L., "Free Vibration of Thick Generally Laminated Cantilever Quadrilateral Plates", *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 34, No. 7, 1996, pp.1474-1486.
9. Liew, K.M., and Lim, C.W., "Vibratory Characteristics of General Laminates, I: Symmetric Trapezoids", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 183, No. 4, 1995, pp. 615-642
10. Liew, K.M., *The Development of 2-D Orthogonal Polynomials for Vibration of Plates*, Ph.D. Thesis, National University of Singapore, Singapore, 1990.
11. Chen, C.C., Liew, K.M., Lim, C.W., and Kitipornchai, S., "Vibration Analysis of Symmetrically Laminated Thick Rectangular Plates Using the Higher-Order Theory and p -Ritz Method", *Journal of the Acoustical society of America*, in press, 1997.